

TEMPERAMENT AS A PERSONALITY STRUCTURE**Jumabaeva Araylim Bakit qizi**

Student of Karakalpak State University

Sagindikova Asemay Batirxan qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15399596>

Abstract. This study examines the temperament of a person and its characteristics. The study analyzes historical approaches to the analysis of the concept of "temperament", as well as various classifications of temperaments. At the same time, the history of the study of the types of temperament of a person, the ideas and theories of scientists are discussed, including individual psychological characteristics such as temperament and psychological defense mechanisms, and the determination of temperament by which of the four elements in the human body predominates.

Keywords: temperament, choleric, sanguine, melancholic, phlegmatic, observation, interview, psychophysiological method, experimental methods, temperament theories, trait, mental process and state.

TEMPERAMENT- SHAXS STRUKTURASI SIFATIDA

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot davomida shaxs temperamentini va uning xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotda "temperament" tushunchasini tahlil qilishning tarixiy yondashuvlari, shuningdek temperamentlarning turli tasniflari tahlil qilinadi. Shu bilan bir qatorda shaxs temperamentining turlari o'rganilish tarixi, olimlarning fikirlari va nazaryalari to'g'risida aytib o'tilgan, shu jumladan temperament kabi individual psixologik xususiyatlari va psixologik himoya mexanizmlari, temperamentning inson tanasidagi to'rtta unsurning qaysi biri ustunlik qilishi bilan belgilanishi tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: temperament, xolerik, sangvinik, melanxolik, flegmatik, kuzatish, suhbat, psixofiziologik usul, eksperimental usullar, temperament nazariyalari, xususiyat, psixik jarayon va holat.

ТЕМПЕРАМЕНТ КАК СТРУКТУРА ЛИЧНОСТИ

Аннотация. В ходе данного исследования изучается темперамент личности и его характеристики. В исследовании анализируются исторические подходы к анализу понятия «темперамент», а также различные классификации темпераментов. При этом рассматривается история изучения типов личности, идеи и теории ученых, проводится анализ таких индивидуальных психологических особенностей, как

темперамент и механизмы психологической защиты, а также то, как темперамент определяется тем, какой из четырех элементов в организме человека преобладает.

Ключевые слова: темперамент, холерик, сангвиник, меланхолик, флегматик, наблюдение, беседа, психофизиологический метод, экспериментальные методы, теории темперамента, черта, психический процесс и состояние.

Introduction

When talking about temperament, they mean many mental differences between people - differences in depth, intensity, stability of emotions, emotional sensitivity, tempo, energy of actions and other dynamic, individually stable features of mental life, behavior and activity. Nevertheless, temperament today remains a controversial and unresolved problem in many ways. However, with all the diversity of approaches to the problem, scientists and practitioners recognize that temperament is a biological foundation on which a person is formed as a social being. The oldest doctrine of temperament belongs to Hippocrates, the “father of medicine.” Hippocrates argued that temperament is determined by which of the four elements that make up the human body predominates. He developed a unique psychophysiological concept that corresponds to ancient views on human nature. He considered each type of temperament to be a psychic expression of the four main fluids in the body: blood (lat. sanguis), bile (chole), phlegm (gr. phlegma) and black bile (melas+chole). Hippocrates, pointing out that temperament is a purely physiological concept, did not associate this phenomenon only with the spiritual whole of the individual. He even considered it quite acceptable to talk about the temperament of individual organs. Another teaching on temperament belongs to Claudius Galen, who lived in the 2nd century BC. His ideas are set out in his famous treatise “De temperamentum” (“On the Right Measure”). Over time, the ideas of Hippocrates and Galen have lost their meaning, but the characteristics of temperament that they described have become firmly established in everyday consciousness. A person whose main element in the body is blood is high-spirited, mobile, excitable, relatively easily experiencing failures and problems, changeable; while the predominance of phlegm in the body characterizes a choleric person, who is capable of working with extraordinary enthusiasm, but is unbalanced, prone to strong emotional outbursts and sudden changes in mood. Temperament reflects dynamic aspects of behavior, mainly of an innate nature, therefore the properties of temperament are the most stable and constant in comparison with other mental characteristics of a person. Analysis of the internal structure of

temperament presents significant difficulties, due to the absence of a single content and a single system of external manifestations in temperament (in its usual psychological characteristics). Attempts at such an analysis lead to the identification of three main, leading, components of temperament, related to the spheres of general activity of the individual, his motor skills and his emotionality. Each of these components, in turn, has a very complex multidimensional structure and different forms of psychological manifestations. Methods for studying personality temperament are carried out in various directions, some of which are scientific, some are practical. Below I will give some of the main methods:

1. Questionnaires and tests One of the most common methods for studying temperament is various psychological tests and questionnaires. For example: Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI) - this test is used to determine the psychological state, temperament and other psychological characteristics of a person. Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ) - this test helps to assess a person's temperament, in particular, the level of extraversion, introversion and neuroticism.

2. Observation (Observation) When studying temperament, psychologists often observe a person in various situations. This method is used to determine a person's responses, actions and reactions to the environment. For example, observing how a person reacts to stress or how he behaves in social situations.

3. Interviews. Conducting interviews is also useful for studying temperament. A psychologist or researcher asks a person questions to learn about their specific behavior, feelings, and thoughts. Interviews can provide more in-depth and individual information about a person's temperament.

4. Lichko's temperament assessment methods. Tests developed by Lichko are used to assess temperament. In this method, a person's personal characteristics and temperament are divided into different categories, and assessments are made based on specific signs.

5. Psychophysiological methods. Sometimes physiological methods are also used to study temperament. For example, by measuring brain activity, monitoring heart rate, blood pressure, and other physiological changes, attempts are made to determine the neurobiological basis of temperament.

6. Experimental methods. Experiments can be conducted to study temperament. In this case, people are tested in certain conditions or under certain stress factors and what responses are obtained from them are observed.

7. Cross-cultural studies. Cross-cultural studies can be conducted to study how temperament varies across cultures and social settings. This method helps to determine how temperament is influenced by cultural influences.

Conclusion

The role of temperament is not the same in different types of activities. In educational activities and in mass professions (turner, mechanic, weaver, salesperson, doctor, teacher, engineer) some properties of temperament, necessary for successful activity and weakly expressed in a given person, can be compensated for by other properties and the work methods conditioned by them. It is also possible for a person to exhibit characteristics of different temperament types in different situations.

Used literature:

1. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.
2. Kurbanova, R. J., and B. E. Saidboeva. "MAKTAB VA OILADA ESTETIK TARBIYANI SHAKLLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA O'QUVCHILARNING AKSIOLOGIK DUNYOQARASHINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Inter education & global study* 9 (2024): 114-121.
3. Jarasovna, Kurbanova Rita. "The Role of National Values in Shaping the Aesthetic Worldview of Schoolchildren." *International Journal of Pedagogics* 5.03 (2025): 55-58.
4. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "USE OF PEDAGOGICAL METHODS BASED ON THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION." *European International Journal of Pedagogics* 4.06 (2024): 26-33.
5. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "Program Technology for Choosing an Effective Educational Methodology Based on Modern Pedagogical Research in The Educational System." *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS* 6.02 (2025): 30-33.
6. Turemuratova, Aziza, Shahlo Matmuratova, and Nargisa Tajieva. "THE DEPENDENCE OF MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES ON PEDAGOGICAL METHODS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN IMPROVING

- STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 50-55.
7. Aziza, Turemuratova. "KONFLIKT VA UNING KELIB CHIQISH SABABLARI." *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке* 3.32 (2025): 457-459.
 8. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza. "PSYCHOLOGICAL CONFIDENTIALITY OF THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES IN EDUCATION." (2025).
 9. Turemuratova, Aziza, Azamat Utambetov, and Rinat Seytimov. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENING ASOSLARI TUSHUNCHASI VA O'SMIRLARNING KOLLOBORATIV KO'NIKMALARINI OSHIRUVCHI PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLAR." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 135-141.
 10. Turemuratova, Aziza, Farog'at Seytmambetova, and Nazokat Masharipova. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARNING USLUBIY MUMMOLARI VA KOLLOBORATIV TA'LIMDA GURUH MUAMMOLARI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 100-106.
 11. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza, and Turganbayeva Amina Quanishbayevna. "PSIXOLOG TRENERNING KASBIY KO'NIKMALARI VA PSIXOLOGIK SALOHIYATINI OSHIRUVCHI AMALIY TRENINGLAR." (2025).
 12. Turemuratova, Aziza, Aynisa Jaqsimuratova, and Ramiza Mustapaeva. "SELF-CONTROL RULES OF A PSYCHOLOGIST-TRAINER." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 217-221.
 13. Muratbayevna, Dauletova Gozal, and Madaminova Nargiza Qurbanbayevna. "BOLANING RIVOJLANISH DAVRI PSIXOLOGIYASI." *Scientific Impulse* 1 (2022): 33-35.
 14. Reyimbaevna, Mambetiyarova Venera, and Jumabayeva Marupa. "OTA-ONA VA FARZANDLAR MUNOSABATINING XUSUSIYATLARI." *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ* 51 (2024): 20-23.